

D1.2

Report on the comparison between
the 11th century vs present

Document Identifier

→D1.2 Report on the comparison
between the 11th century vs present

Date Due

→M26

Submission Date

→30th april 2021

Work Package 1

→ Narratives of the Self

Lead Beneficiary

→10-Radboud

This project has received
the European union's
Horizon 2020 research and
innovation programme under
the Marie Skłodowska-Curie
grant agreement N°813547.

ITN-MIDA 813547

Introduction

The objective of work package 1 “[Narratives of the Self](#)” is to study the way technological revolutions have informed the performance of selfhood (male and female), modes of engagement with society, and the political consequences of shifting boundaries between public and private spheres. In order to do so we track in the various sources (manuscripts, v/blogs, clips) the indications of new forms of selfhood.

In this second deliverable the three ESR’s particularly focus on 1. the technological form of self-narratives of their specific studies as well as 2. the (new) forms of selfhood and self-narrative they have found, taking into account the possible intersectional identities such as gender.

ESR 1 Mohamed El-Moursi

1. The ‘technological’ form of self-narratives

As late as the eighth century, parchment and papyrus were the main materials for making Arabic books. The situation changed with the importation of paper-making from china to Baghdad (Elayyan, 1990).

By the beginning of the third/ninth century, paper has become an alternative to these materials. The technique of paper making spread through the main cities in Islamic World, and, consequently, the number of bookmaker or bookshops expanded in Islamic cities. This meant that more books could be produced at a less expensive price, and they can easily be distributed to different cities.

The bookshops or book markets also were centers for writing, copying, and translation; as well as it became the meeting places for scholars (Elayyan, 1990; Bloom, 2001). In al-Andalus, for instance, paper making arrived by the mid of the fourth/tenth century, and, since then, the book industry had become an essential sector of the economy (Ramjaun, 2020).

Paper mills seem to be diffused all over the Andalusian cities such as Toledo and Granada. Some cities were even known for their book markets in which men of letters were searched about the rare editions (Qaysī, 1989).

2. The (new) forms of selfhood - self-narrative

To some extent, one could say that the production of paper in the Islamicate societies led to a wide circulation of first-person autobiographical texts written by famous figures. The industrially manufactured paper resulted in the production of cheaper books which stimulated greater interest in scientific and literary studies (Ramjaun, 2020).

Scholars, like Reynolds et al and Rosenthal, have stressed several reasons for the production of multiple autobiographical texts. These reasons range from the personal connections of writers to the tremendous political instability of some periods which may have “helped to foster a fertile context for autobiographical production” (Reynolds et al, 2001).

They, however, did not pay attention to the technological dimension, paper-making, which facilitated the circulation of autobiographical texts and made it possible. In other words, the production of paper was an essential reason for the deliberation of first-person

autobiographical texts among writers and the establishment of the pre-modern autobiographical tradition.

During the late twelfth and early thirteenth centuries, for example, a large number of autobiographies were prompted by the aforementioned factors. A group who lived in Damascus and Aleppo wrote a cluster of distinctive and noteworthy autobiographical texts. Those were: ‘Umāra al-Hakamī al-Yamanī (d. 1175); Usāma ibn Munqidh (d. 1188); ‘Imād al-Dīn al-Kātib al-Isfahānī (d. 1201); Yāqūt al-Hamawī (d. 1229); ‘Abd al-Laṭīf al-Baghdādī (d. 1231); Ibn al-‘Adīm (d. 1262); Abū Shāma (d. 1268); and Sa’d al-Dīn ibn Hamawiyya al-Juwaynī (d. 1276). They were all aware of one another’s writings. For instance, ‘Imād al-Dīn quotes from ‘Umāra’s autobiography in his works; and “Yāqūt personally commissioned the autobiography of his close friend, Ibn al-‘Adīm, for inclusion in his compendium” (Reynolds et al, 2001).

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2. The (new) forms of selfhood - self-narrative

It may be also worth noting that one of the earliest books on bookmaking was written by al-Mu'izz ibn Bādīs (406/1016-454/1062), the Zīrid prince of Ifrīqiya. No evidence, however, that the Zīrid emir Ibn Buluggīn who wrote his memoir, *The Tibyān*, read the book; but most probably he must have heard of it due to the connection between the Zīrid family. He himself narrated the departure of Zāwī ibn Zīrī's (410/1019) departure for Ifrīqiya which took place during the realm of al-Mu'izz (Ibn Buluggīn, *The Tibyān*).

Yet, the impact of technology on writing/narrating the self is still, to some extent, a neglected aspect that is missing in the studies of pre-modern knowledge production and writing autobiographies.

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ESR 2 Lena Richter

1. The ‘technological’ form of self-narratives of Moroccan nonbelievers

The technological resources available also impact the forms of self-narratives for different minority groups, such as Moroccan nonbelievers. Around the 11th century, only very few non- or less religious thinkers, such as Al-Ma’arri (973-1057) were able to express and spread their thoughts about Islam on a larger scale. With the printing revolution, the possibilities to reach a wider audience increased but remained among those privileged enough to read, write, and print.

Today, books continue to form an important tool for nonbelievers but are still no medium of the mass. While it is possible to publish under a pseudonym most of the self-narratives are written by well-known, public, and outspoken nonbelievers, such as Hicham Nostik (2020) who wrote the autobiographical book “Dialogue with the Muslim in me”.

Digitalization has drastically changed the self-narratives of Moroccan non-believers. While some digital platforms remain

rather used by a few, rather vocal, nonbelievers, others are accessible to a larger group. On the one hand, YouTube channels, such as kafer maghribi, blogs, such as il7ad and podcasts, such as Secular Jihadists are mainly initiated by activist nonbelievers.

Also (auto)biographical films are mainly about well known former Muslims, such as the documentary “Betty/ Letter 4049: F”, about the nonreligious activist and founder of the MALI movement Ibtissame Betty Lachgar. On the other hand, Facebook, and especially private and hidden Facebook groups offer a platform for ordinary nonbelievers to share their self-narratives online.

Thus, digitalization has led to a democratization of narratives: it has become more accessible to a broader and diverse group of people to share their stories and to reach, if intended, a huge audience within little time. While not everyone might have the opportunity or skills to write a book, it is relatively easy to create a post on Facebook or Twitter.

This development has led to a new visibility of nonbelievers in Morocco and the whole WANA region.

Self-narratives did not only become more accessible but also changed in form. For instance, nonbelievers expressed more frequently, interactively, and shortly their thoughts and feelings instead of a classical monograph. In the digital age, the technological medium further determines the length and style of online self-narratives in several ways.

For example, the character length to express oneself ranges from 280 characters on Twitter to 83,206 characters on Facebook. While some mediums are more textual, like blogs, other platforms, like Instagram offer more visual possibilities. Another distinction can be made between more interactive mediums, such as Twitter and more one-directional communication used in YouTube channels and podcasts.

ESR 2 Lena Richter

2. The (new) forms of selfhood - self-narrative - concepts of self, taking into account the possible intersectional identities like gender etc.

Digitalization gave space for the expressions of different virtual selves, especially in private spaces, such as closed Facebook groups.

Looking at these self-narratives, different self-frames become clear, such as 1) the enlightened philosopher; 2) the human rights activist; 3) the doubter; 4) the struggler; 5) the postcolonial, and 6) the liberalist.

Let me elaborate on these different types a bit further: First, the enlightened philosopher prioritizes logical, rational, and scientific aspects of their identity, for instance by making statements such as the Quran is illogical and stressing the importance of science and philosophy.

Second, the nonreligious human rights activist frames themselves as an advocate for queer, women, and secular rights. Among others, they mention in their

self-narrative aspects of Islam which they perceive as myogenic and which, therefore, made them leave Islam.

Third, the doubter questions everything including religion but also their own position towards religion. For them, nonreligion does not need to be the terminal in their searching process. The doubter is torn between different positions and points at struggles in their way to find their right position.

Fourth, this is also the case for the struggler, who underlines that leaving Islam can be very hard and difficult on a psychological and societal level. The strugglers' self-narratives focus on common and personal problems that nonbelievers experience, such as family issues, having to hide their nonbelief, being obligated to leave the family's house, or not being able to eat during Ramadan.

Fifth, the postcolonial self stresses that nonreligion can be something Moroccan, for instance, by referring to the Amazigh history and movement and by pointing out that Islam has spread to Morocco in the 7th century. In doing so, they also refuse to see nonreligion as a Western idea and are critical of the concept of laïcité which they associate with the former colonizer France.

Finally, the liberalist self sees non/religious identification as a personal choice. According to the self-narrative of liberalists, everyone is free to choose whatever they want. They also apply this for their own ideas about raising children, teaching them about different religions and nonreligion and letting them make their own choice. They also argue for having a school curriculum that teaches about different religions.

Of course, this list of self-narratives is neither exhaustive nor clearly defined. Individuals can prioritize and combine self-narratives according to their own opinions, positionalities, and relational situations.

In relatively safe online spaces, out of the sight of family members or political surveillance, former Muslims can share their personal thoughts and experiences more freely and apply different self-frames. Yet, questions remain if these new digital forms of self-expression are truly inclusive. For instance, if female non-believers use the opportunity to share their self-narratives online, as much as their male counterparts.

ESR 3 Rayane Al-Rammal

1. The ‘technological’ form of self-narratives

Characterized by moments of “freedom, egalitarianism, communion, and creativity” (Yang, 2000), social movements work as liminal periods that hold the potentiality of transfiguring participants’ self-narratives. Moreover, their resulting cultural practices work as liminal spaces where these narratives might be creatively reshaped and expressed (Stenner & Zittoun, 2020).

Fueled by rampant corruption caused by almost thirty years of post-war rule by a sectarian oligarchic elite, the October 17 Lebanese Intifada has allegedly sparked epistemological changes in the way protestors relate to the nation-state but more so to their self-narratives. In a highly segregated country, protestors were renouncing their traditional sectarian leaders and defying an oppressive exploitative political system that violently suppresses dissent (HRW, 2020).

When closely examining this recent social movement, one could argue that it manifested essential features of liminality whereas it was an ambivalent volatile situation offering the potentiality of the “embryonic formation of a *communitas*” (Georgsen, M., & Thomassen, 2017).

A new self-narrative was thus reimagined and enacted through protests. Moreover, when the uprising broke out, it unleashed a crescendo of contentious art especially on digital spaces and mainly on the platform of Instagram. I argue that these artistic forms of activism (artivism) could also function as a space of liminality, which reflects the one experienced and indeed needed in social change.

“I Don’t Want to Fear Love and the Revolution”: Digital Artivism of the Lebanese Intifada 2019 on Instagram as a Technological Form of Queer Self-Narratives

Moreover, Instagram (the medium through which this artivism is received and/or created) could equally be thought of as offering a liminal zone for its high cultural and ritualistic character, leaving us thus with triple liminality of a social movement, its art, and the platform of Instagram. This triple liminality was key to the emergence of new technological forms of self-narratives.

For instance, it offered a space for marginalized communities to re-enter the public sphere. Almost a year and a half after the uprising, and in the context of a global pandemic that restricts face-to-face interactions and people’s physical access to the city (Schoorel & Luitjens & van der Reijden, 2019), many of the contentious conversations are moving to the digital spaces that are working as an extension to squares of the revolution enacting, therefore, a specific technological form of self-narratives, namely a digital artivistic one.

ESR 3 Rayane Al-Rammal

2. The (new) forms of selfhood - self-narrative - concepts of self, taking into account the possible intersectional identities like gender, etc.

For the very first time in the modern history of Lebanon, many people living in sectarian-segregated regions have shared the squares of the uprising together. Marginalized groups have also found themselves sharing space with other protestors.

For instance, queer communities who were structurally and violently excluded from the political terrain have “entered the mainstream as a pillar of resistance for the first time” (Younes, 2019). In a country where authorities have relentlessly policed their existence, they became part and parcel of the Lebanese intifada (Younes, 2019).

Anti-gay sentiment is widely perpetuated in the Lebanese community as 80% of the Lebanese reject homosexuality (Pew Research Center, 2013). But in the liminality of the protests, the streets that were once associated with fear and anxiety for queer people became less hostile. Adding to this, following the burst of the people’s anger,

there was a culmination of artistic creation in which gender-related questions were very present. On the walls of the revolution, words and images were celebrating sexual and gender diversity (Al-Bawaba, 2019) and even responding to some sexist revolutionary slogans.

Even before the intifada, there were many artists’ pages on Instagram (like Queer Arabs for example) celebrating non-normative gender identities on the internet. But it is namely the triple liminality of the social movement, art, and the internet which allowed new technological forms of queer self-narratives to emerge in alignment with the uprising.

These digital spaces were used as counter-safe spaces to create and share queer artistic activism to counter status-quo oppression. Instagram was used as a site for symbolic and political resistance, where queer artists reclaimed intragroup alliances to foster their representation in the mainstream

narratives of the uprising. They viewed their demands as connecting the struggles against patriarchal, capitalist, colonialist systems. And even though this belief was not shared among the protestors, there was a growing consciousness of their existence, namely due to this new technological form of self-narratives.

Illustration Credits from left to right: @nougature, @queerarabs and, @rawandissa

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